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Inguinal abscess revealing an incarcerated cecal tumor: a rare clinical presentation

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ABSTRACT :

The discovery of a colonic tumor, particularly a cecal tumor, within an inguinal hernia is exceptional, especially when complicated by septic evolution. This rare situation poses significant diagnostic and therapeutic défis, particularly in an emergency setting.

We report the case of a female patient admitted for a painful right inguinal mass, without signs of bowel obstruction. Surgical exploration revealed a perforated cecal adenocarcinoma incarcerated within the inguinal canal, complicated by a local abscess. Emergency surgical management was performed, adhering to the principles of infection control, oncological resection, and hernia repair adapted to the septic context.

Intrahernial colonic tumors represent a rare cause of incarcerated inguinal hernia. Preoperative diagnosis is often difficult, making imaging—particularly computed tomography—essential. The surgical strategy is not standardized and must be individualized according to the patient's condition, intraoperative findings, and the risk of infection.

The association of an incarcerated inguinal hernia with complicated colonic cancer is rare and represents a true défi in emergency surgery. Reporting such cases contributes to a better understanding of this entity and to the optimization of its management.

Keywords: Cecal tumor , Inguinal hernia , Incarcerated inguinal hernia , Sliding hernia , Hernia sac tumor , Inguinal abscess

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Introduction :

Inguinal hernias are common in general surgery; however, the discovery of a colonic neoplastic lesion within the hernia sac remains exceptional. The most frequently reported sites include the sigmoid colon, the cecum, and the appendix. These presentations may be complicated by incarceration, perforation, and abscess formation, making preoperative diagnosis difficult.[1]

We report the case of an incarcerated cecal adenocarcinoma within the inguinal canal, complicated by a local abscess, and analyze its diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in light of the available literature. This unusual presentation, combining an incidental discovery with an exceptional septic evolution, represents a major challenge both in terms of diagnosis and surgical management.

Case report :

A 72-year-old woman, followed for glaucoma under medical treatment, presented to the emergency department with right iliac fossa pain associated with vomiting and the appearance of a painful inguinal mass that had been evolving for 3 days, without bowel transit disorders or externalized gastrointestinal bleeding.

Clinical examination revealed a 10 cm inguinal swelling that was fluctuant, erythematous, warm, and tender, associated with right iliac fossa tenderness. An ultrasound examination was performed, showing a collection in the right iliac fossa measuring $49 \times 56 \times 109$ mm, appearing to communicate with a 17×28 mm parietal collection as well as with a right colonic mass.

An abdomino-pelvic CT scan was then performed, revealing a well-defined right abdomino-inguinal collection measuring 9×6 cm and extending over 10 cm. This collection was in intimate contact with the anteroinferior wall of the cecum, which showed a circumferential wall thickening measuring 15 mm over a length of 30 mm (Figure 1).

Figure 1 : A CT scan image showing a right abdomino-inguinal collection in contact with the cecum (blue arrow)

Biological tests showed a normal hemoglobin level, elevated white blood cell count at $14,000/\text{mm}^3$, and an increased CRP level of 149.3 mg/L. The hydroelectrolytic balance was within normal limits.

Based on these findings, the decision was made to proceed with urgent surgical intervention. The patient was rapidly transferred to the operating room.

The surgical procedure was performed in two stages. The first, inguinal stage involved an inguinal incision that revealed a collection of approximately 200 cc of pus, which was drained and evacuated, along with a perforated cecum adherent to the inguinal floor (Figure 2).

The second, abdominal stage revealed a tumoral-looking thickening of the cecal base, perforated at the level of the inguinal floor (Figure 3), with the presence of ileocecal lymphadenopathy as well as a small amount of peritoneal effusion. However, there were no hepatic or peritoneal nodules, nor any other digestive wall thickening.

Figure 2 : Intraoperative images showing a perforated cecum

Figure 3 : Intraoperative image showing a perforated cecum adherent to the inguinal floor

Right ileohemicolectomy according to oncologic principles was performed, followed by creation of an ileocolostomy and repair of the right inguinal hernia using the Bassini technique.

Histopathological examination of the surgical specimen revealed a moderately differentiated invasive adenocarcinoma, NOS type, with a mucinous component (less than 50%), infiltrating the full thickness of the cecal wall with serosal perforation. Perineural invasion was present. There was evidence of intra- and extramural venous emboli as well as lymphatic emboli. Both ileal and colonic resection margins were free of tumor. No lymph node metastasis was identified (0/20 lymph nodes).

Postoperative recovery was uneventful. The patient was mobilized on postoperative day 1, and the stoma became functional on postoperative day 2. She was discharged on postoperative day 3 in good general condition and referred to the oncology department for further management.

Discussion :

The incidence of inguinal hernias in Western populations is high, at approximately 1.7%. In addition, the incidence of colorectal cancer in Western populations is 40 per 100,000 and it currently represents the fourth leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide. However, the association between both conditions is rare, with only 38 cases reported in the literature [2].

Although inguinal hernia is a common condition, its irreducible form is less frequent and may be complicated by intestinal obstruction or strangulation. The association with malignancy is exceptional. Tumors associated with inguinal hernias are classically divided into saccular forms, arising from the hernia sac itself, and intrasacculary forms, corresponding to tumors of herniated organs [3], as observed in our case.

Our case specifically involved the development of a large abscess cavity outside the hernia sac. Benfatto et al. [1] reported a similar case. We hypothesize the mechanism of subcutaneous abscess formation as follows: the cecal tumor invaded the peritoneum (hernia sac) and perforated into the extraperitoneal space (subcutaneous tissue) [3].

Although primary colonic malignancy within an inguinal hernia sac has been rarely reported, our extensive literature review identified 12 cases of perforated colonic cancer within an inguinal hernia sac [1, 4–13].

This entity most commonly presents as a long-standing right inguinal hernia that becomes painful or incarcerated [14]. In our case, the patient reported recent onset of a right groin mass without signs of bowel obstruction and without any history of inguinal hernia or known neoplasia. Diagnosis may be challenging, particularly in elderly patients, making computed tomography essential to confirm suspicion of underlying malignancy [14].

ElShamarka A. (2025) conducted a systematic review on the presentation of colorectal cancer within inguinal hernias. This analysis, including 40 patients from the literature, reported a male predominance, an advanced mean age, and a preferential involvement of the sigmoid colon. Surgical management most often consisted of colonic resection combined with hernia repair performed in a single-stage operation. A diversion stoma was created in nearly half of the cases, with no significant influence of prosthesis use on this indication. Overall, postoperative morbidity was low in most series. These data suggest that combining oncologic resection with hernia repair is feasible but must be adapted to the clinical context, particularly the septic risk and the patient's condition [15].

The optimal surgical management remains controversial and must be individualized, taking into account patient characteristics such as age and general condition, the local tumor extension (visceral or vascular

involvement), and the surgeon's expertise. In most reported cases in the literature, colonic resection via laparotomy is followed by inguinal hernia repair, performed through two separate incisions [14, 16].

Inguinal hernia repair requires strictly clean operative conditions, whereas colorectal cancer resection is considered a clean-contaminated procedure, or even contaminated in cases of tumor perforation. In this context, the use of biological mesh is generally discouraged. Primary suture repair may be considered using standard techniques, with the choice tailored to the patient's condition to reduce postoperative infectious risk. However, some authors have reported cautious use of biological meshes in selected cases, allowing reduced postoperative pain and recurrence rates, provided that no perforation or peritoneal contamination is present [16].

Conclusion :

An incarcerated inguinal hernia associated with a perforated colonic cancer, particularly cecal, is a rare and complex entity. Its management relies on emergency surgical intervention, integrating infection control, adherence to oncological principles, and a safe and appropriate hernia repair. The absence of a therapeutic consensus justifies an individualized approach based on intraoperative findings and the surgeon's experience.

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